

Reflections on Ensuring Financial Stability in the Context of Globalization

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Abstract

In the present days, globalization represents a challenge for society because it requires assimilation and control of the relevant content and information that is transmitted by building links between diverse economies and communities. Globalization is facilitated by the free movement of money, labor, and technology. The intensification of global economic exchanges increases the dependence of emerging economies on developed economies, which have a large share of capital and expertise in many areas. Achieving financial stability by a financial system is conditioned by the absence of an economic and financial crisis, but also by the ability of the system to limit the impact of negative effects and deterioration of the system before it poses a threat to systemic stability. The aim of this paper is to investigate how financial stability is ensured in the context of globalization based on reviewing previous research in this field. The first part of the paper analyses the notion and the dynamics of financial globalization. The second part of the paper investigates the theoretical and practical challenges of financial stability in the current context of globalization. Moreover, it presents a series of measures that contribute to maintaining financial stability.

Keywords: financial deregulation, financial stability, globalization, market economy.

Introduction

In economic theory, the debates on the emergence of the phenomenon of globalization revolve around three major approaches: globalization has always existed, but recently began to increase its pace of manifestation and expand its coverage (Dreher, Gaston & Martens, 2008); globalization is contemporaneous with the modern state and the development of the market economy, being marked by a recent acceleration (Amin, 2014); globalization is a recent phenomenon, associated with other social phenomena such as post-industrial, postmodern society, in the context of the failures and disorganization of capitalism (Bradley, 2015). Financial globalization is the link between the economies affected by crisis (Broner & Ventura, 2016), given that globalization is by definition interdependence, system, and contagion, when relations between states deteriorate due to the difficulties of one or more partners of these relations. Thus, there is a polarization between pro-globalists and anti-globalists in terms of the potential benefits of globalization (Flejterski, 2018): pro-globalists believe that globalization has eminently positive effects on the standard of living of the population (Bowles, 2017), on its income through diversification, but also by liberalizing labor movement, capital and technology. While pro-globalists argue that the main beneficiaries of globalization are poor countries, anti-globalists have antagonistic beliefs that globalization has devastating effects on poor countries because it affects local culture, the environment, and the quality of life (Griva & Chrysoschoou, 2015).

Globalization is a complex process determined by multiple causes, given the diversity of the contemporary world and the international relations developed between modern societies, the spatial or temporal distance no longer being an obstacle to the expansion of transnational relations (Burlacu, Gutu & Matei, 2018; Martin et al., 2018). Politically, globalization stands as a threat to poorer countries, which are exploited by large economies (Adams et al., 2019). There is also a transfer of power from the state to multinational corporations, which is currently concentrating financial power (Cohen, 2018).

Globalization means the intensification of social relations spread globally, which connect places at almost immeasurable distances, but which are influenced by events that occur at great physical distance, which would otherwise be impossible to annihilate (Robinson, 2007). They occur as follows: relocation and supra territoriality; the transmission of technological innovations is done with an incumbent speed (Dima, 2021) and a

certain risk; domination of multinational corporations; liberalization and development of financial markets lead to a corresponding increase in the risk exposures of national economies.

The phenomenon is a positive one due to the contribution of economic growth potential it offers to the interconnected states (Porter, 2000; Majeed et al., 2021), leading to the increase of living standards. Economic integration leads to a better division of labor between integrated states (Drysdale & Garnaut, 2022), a mechanism that allows low-wage economies to specialize in diverse and competitive fields, while developed countries with a high-wage policy increase labor productivity by enabling companies to exploit economies of scale. Globalization also allows for the migration of capital flows to the highest-yielding investment opportunities (Avi-Yonah, 2000), without being forced to be placed in the country of origin at lower returns. Globalization is also a paradox, due to the fact that it reduces the world to a compressed whole, due to the compression of temporal and spatial barriers, but also an intensification of awareness that the world becomes a much more complex set of forces, due to the interdependencies that form (Pakulski & Waters, 1996). Globalization brings advantages to the national economies integrated in this indefinite superstructure (Bello, 2017), which allows the diversity, but also the homogeneity of local practices and cultures. Globalization increases the competitiveness of local producers (Dima, 2018), who can therefore develop their businesses (Trifu, Girneata & Potcovaru, 2014). Also, globalization facilitates the free movement of labor (Girneata, 2015), and increases the employment opportunities.

The relocation can also be seen in the banking system, where financial advances and infrastructure have enabled the creation of a portion of banking activity that does not require physical interaction between the bank and the customer. Not everything, though, is globalized. In a globalized system of inputs and outputs, employment is generally local or regional, but it is undoubtedly influenced by strategic activities and economic reasons.

Apart from the benefits of the phenomenon, globalization has the potential to suppress frontiers and the sovereignty of developed countries' preferences and interests, resulting in inequitable resource allocation, unfair redistribution of national product, intensifying differences and differences between social strata, and the dominance of the few and large over the small and many.

The magnitude of globalization is leading researchers to address the issue of a "new world economy," pointing out the problems facing a globalized system, stating that it is not the problems themselves that have the greatest negative impact on the world economy, but the two fundamental components that have exacerbated them, namely the population and the economy (Clapham, 2002; Berkowitz, Pistor & Richard, 2003; Vorontsova et al., 2018). Among the problems we mention: deforestation, biodiversity loss, future scarcity of natural resources such as water, poverty, carbon emissions, etc. The new world economy, amid the evolution of technology and economic and financial conditions, involves much faster and more flexible production processes (Girneata & Dobrin, 2015), the multiplication of alliances and partnerships, the expansion of the service sector and the generalization of teleservices, the complete restructuring of enterprises and new types of products and services, generating both opportunities and threats for the states involved.

Research Methodology and Objectives

The main aim of the present paper is to investigate how financial stability can be ensured in the context of the complex phenomenon of globalization. The research methodology that was used is systematic review of previous research in this field. Namely, various articles, books and reports that investigate this topic of interest and the results were summarized and objectively analyzed below.

The secondary objectives of the current paper are the following:

- Investigating the notion and the dynamics of financial globalization;
- Analyzing the theoretical and practical challenges of financial stability in the current context of globalization;

- Highlighting the most important measures that contribute to maintaining financial stability.

According to these stated secondary objectives, the information in the following section of this article is structured to present the main findings for each part.

The notion of financial globalization

Financial globalization represents the most essential aspect of globalization, particularly in light of the unstable global financial system, but it is also vulnerable to external threats. Globalization must be viewed as a process rather than a system situation. This entails a quantitative and qualitative increase in some trade transactions outside of national borders, such as on international financial-banking markets. Financial globalization not only helps to increase consumption and investment in geographically distant financial markets, but it also helps to diversify risk by decompartmentalizing markets.

The dynamics of financial globalization must also be analyzed in the light of the risk component of interbank exposures in a market or of international exposures that generate systemic risk. Many theorists as well as economic practitioners appreciate that the most recent global financial crisis was caused only by the collapse of the real estate market (Obstfeld & Rogoff, 2009; Jackson, 2018), due to the moral hazard of customers, who took risks without coverage because they did not have enough information (information asymmetry) on the market and could not predict the evolution of real estate prices amid excessive demand for mortgages (Baily, Litan & Johnson, 2008; Harrington, 2009). In essence, however, the bursting of speculative bubbles was due to a longer process of accumulation of imbalances, which decompensated, affecting the entire economy (Mateo & Revuelto, 2018).

Financial globalization, seen as one of the other dimensions of the phenomenon, designates the interdependent relationships that are formed between banking systems and financial markets globally. An important role in the globalization process is played by financial deregulation, which involves relaxing regulations in the financial-banking field, which does not mean eliminating them, but allowing banking institutions to pursue profit maximization with a greater margin of maneuver, especially in terms of interest rates on deposits and loans granted. Regarding deregulation, two main aspects are significant: the amplitude of the intervention on the financial-banking market and the allowed or chosen intervention instruments.

In the literature there are three ideological trends specific to the 1990s, which Held, McGrew, Goldblatt and Perraton identify and highlight their limitations (Held et al., 2000).

The **hyperglobalist perspective** amplifies the role of globalization in building a new era of humanity, dominated by the lack of borders between national economies, all being part of a global market. National authority is repealed and economies are denationalized.

The **skeptical perspective** classifies the current phenomenon of globalization as a process of regionalization and fragmentation, exemplifying this ideology with the third world, which is marginalized rather than integrated into a global market. The authors also point out that the development of multinational corporations brings benefits to their host countries, not being outsourced as an employed workforce.

The **transformative perspective** does not identify any real reasoning behind globalization, nor any result, being at the opposite pole of the other two currents of thought.

The operations intensified by the process of financial globalization refer to the integration of both the public and the private sector in a developed, complex global financial market, so to the involvement of public and private institutions in cross-border financial transactions (cross-border). State loans and foreign direct investment become international financial flows, along with acquisitions and mergers between certain financial institutions. Looser regulations or financial deregulation have fostered increased capital inflows and outflows between states around the world.

Financial globalization, as one of the phenomenon's other elements, refers to the worldwide interdependent links that exist between banking systems and financial markets. Financial deregulation, which entails loosening financial-banking regulations (not eliminating them), but allowing banking institutions to pursue profit maximization with more leeway, particularly in terms of interest rates on deposits and loans granted, plays an important role in the globalization process.

Liberalization of capital flows poses a risk to states that conduct a substantial volume of international trade, in which foreign capital flows are large or capital outflows are large, if exports are boosted, and emphasis is paid to specific intermediate or operational goals. Monetary policy should be tightened. The capital account's full deregulation is contingent on:

- External competitiveness must be bolstered by state policymakers' credibility; the budget deficit must be kept within prudential bounds;
- The level of external debt should not imperil the government's solvency;
- Encouraging competition through fiscal and monetary policies in order to boost domestic output and, implicitly, GDP;
- Inflation targeting, which puts financial stability at risk if the objective is not met;
- The exchange rate is controlled to some extent by the monetary authority, so that in the event of a significant appreciation or depreciation of the national currency, which has an impact on capital movements, the monetary authority intervenes;
- The availability of established, up-to-date information systems that respond to current needs for assessing the state of the economy in general, as well as monitoring and developing correlations between specific economic problems in order to give ethnic support for substantiating remedies.

Financial stability - theoretical and practical challenges in the current context of globalization

The peculiarities of a financial system reveal the dynamism and uncertainties that hover over its evolution and not every turbulence becomes continuous and degenerates into an episode of instability. Competent authorities, in general monetary authorities, are working to overcome the imbalance and reach a new financial equilibrium through certain measures (Bernanke, 2020). Obviously, a set of preventive measures need to be implemented, which generate lower costs than corrective or remedial ones. The state of normalcy or stability is what most often characterizes the financial system, with self-regulatory mechanisms at its disposal (Brunnermeier & Sannikov, 2014). When they are overcome, authorities can intervene, for example through conventional and/or unconventional monetary policy instruments (Reichlin, 2021), such as liquidity injection operations, to reduce the negative effects of exogenous shocks and restore endogenous balance.

Financial stability is also based on the expectations of market players, being a dynamic, globalized phenomenon, conditioned by numerous financial conditions, but also by technological progress and innovations in the financial field (Adrian & Shin, 2008; Tarullo, 2019). What is stable at some point in time becomes unstable due to changes in social, political, technological, so we can see financial stability as a lot of combinations of conditions and constituent factors, such as the health of financial institutions, the efficiency of infrastructure, financial, investor expectations, the evolution of monetary targets, etc.

There is a causal link between economic growth and the stability of the financial system (Younsi & Bechtini, 2018; Guru & Yadav, 2019). On the one hand, the efficient allocation of financial resources within the system, as well as the optimization of savings and investment processes can facilitate the development of the economy (Qiang & Jian, 2020). On the other hand, the financial system is affected by the performance of the real economy. Given these interdependencies, not every malfunction of the financial market or of an individual institution is widespread, with an impact on the economy as a whole. For example, the bankruptcy of a small financial institution or an increase in asset price volatility may be the result of competitive forces, the absorption of new information into the market, and therefore the result of market discipline and market self-regulation. Also, the level of regulation impacts upon other aspects of the economy such as the start - up of new businesses

(Trifu, Gîrneală & Potcovaru, 2015). In the absence of significant contagion or exposure to systemic risk, such turbulence is often welcome to restore system stability.

The challenge is to strike the right balance for a "pure" financial stability (Debrun & Jonung, 2019). The opposite of financial stability, ie financial instability, is often associated with the notions of vulnerability or fragility, none of which are indispensable in a financial system, because the component of volatility and risk is intrinsic and immutable, and what differs is only the size of the risk and the capacity of the system to absorb it with the least effort. Thus, regardless of the state of the financial system, namely normality, pre-crisis, crisis, post-crisis, it is characterized by a certain level of fragility and vulnerability. Of course, the state of financial stability implies a low level of risk of destabilization due to the fragility and vulnerability of the system (Hamdaoui & Maktouf, 2020).

The fragility of the financial system refers to the situation in which the system can be destabilized due to internal, endogenous shocks (Amountzias, 2019), while the vulnerability involves its risky exposure to external conditions, which can disrupt the state of normalcy (Gertler, Kiyotaki & Queralto, 2012). Thus, financial instability is the result of the acute manifestation of fragility and vulnerability and is practically the effect of these two causes.

The vulnerabilities to which a financial system is exposed are related to its components, namely the market, individual financial institutions and the infrastructure or interface between the financial operations that take place in the market and the market stakeholders. These are practically endogenous factors, while the external environment is the exogenous component. Among the multitude of potential vulnerabilities, we mention the asymmetry of information that characterizes the financial market, risks related to infrastructure, given the importance of the proper functioning of payment systems, risks related to political instability, unclear regulation of financial activities. In most cases, external vulnerabilities are related to exchange rate volatility, the deterioration of the balance of payments situation, and therefore the risk of a currency crisis. The stability of all components of the financial system becomes an important stake in the conditions of the liberalization of the financial systems. The phenomenon of globalization is increasing competitive pressures, which is causing risky behavior on the part of the financial services industry.

Measures that contribute to maintaining financial stability

The measures that can be adopted and implemented fall into two categories, namely **preventive measures**, aimed at correcting and reducing the vulnerabilities ex ante triggering a crisis episode and **corrective or remedial measures** (Crockett, 1996; Schinasi, 2004; Jones & Knaack, 2019). The latter have the role of acting ex post, when preventive measures have not prevented the emergence of a widespread imbalance and reduce the adverse effects of the instability that the financial system is going through.

The **preventive measures** are intended to control the risk of financial instability, to anticipate key points of the system and to act on their ex-ante correction. These measures cover the size of the financial infrastructure and are not necessarily related to the financial size of the problems facing individual institutions. This category of measures covers issues related to the regulation of financial activities, market discipline, the provision of information to regulate information asymmetry, but also physical infrastructure.

First of all, the regulation of banking activity requires legislation both to protect depositors and banking institutions. Legal constraints can discourage investment, but caution is the best way to prevent losses. The provision of public information helps to increase the transparency of financial activities and to combat the asymmetry of information, as it has the role of informing the public concerned about the micro and macroeconomic developments of an economy or financial system. This materializes in the publication of the results obtained following empirical studies developed by specialists, the evolution of macroeconomic variables, by identifying fiscal and/or monetary pressures that threaten the economic and social development of a country.

If the implementation of preventive measures has not been carried out effectively, then the financial stability of the system may be threatened, making it necessary to implement the following category of measures, namely remedial or corrective measures. **Remedial measures** include financial assistance to individual institutions in the form of liquidity and solvency support, which is used by the central bank as a lender or lender of last resort.

Liquidity support consists in the exercise by the monetary authority of the right and obligation to inject liquidity into the system, in order to regain the dynamic financial balance. For example, if the financial infrastructure has difficulty operating at a particular institution, then the central bank supports that bank by injecting liquidity and absorbing the losses incurred. This is also the role of the monetary council, if it has decided to set the exchange rate of national currencies against the single euro.

Solvency is the form of a concrete manifestation of the static financial balance and refers to the debtor's ability to pay its outstanding obligations on account of the available resources. Therefore, solvency implies both a lack of liquidity and an inability to use other sources to meet payment obligations. The problem of insolvency becomes even more pressing for the financial system as the insolvent institution becomes more important for the real economy. In this case, the government may end up supporting the affected financial or non-financial institution, taking into account the effects of the contagion phenomenon. Therefore, the state protects the real economy from the impact of the insolvency of a large institution, but also protects creditors, who would otherwise have recorded a significant volume of losses from non-performing exposures. This type of emergency assistance raises the issue of moral hazard, as such unconventional measures can set a bad precedent, an accumulation of public debt, but also a safeguarding practice that should be exceptional and not current.

In addition to preventive and remedial measures, there is another category of measures whose effective implementation could be a pattern, a reference system for the emergence of new potential episodes of financial instability. These measures aim to change the fundamentals of the financial system according to its vulnerabilities and dysfunctions, being a measure of structural change (Nelson & Perli, 2007; Hellwig, 2009; Hamdaoui & Maktouf, 2020), for example:

- crisis management measures. These measures become necessary immediately after the onset of the financial crisis, when no other measures have proved effective. These measures can be used in the case of previous financial crises, if their manifestation is similar, affecting the same real variables in the economy. At this point, a critical analysis of the economic and financial situation of the system, the prioritization of adverse effects in order of priorities for the competent authorities, the identification of solutions and alternatives, as well as the urgency of implementing corrective measures, but also the identification of competent authorities in interventions. from the country or other Member States, depending on the severity of the problem;
- identifying the determinants of the crisis and reducing their influence. The cyclical nature of the economy, the behavior of financial institutions, the measures implemented in the event of a crisis of global importance, does not mean challenging the uniqueness of a crisis and its form of manifestation. Thus, the measures that are often required have no correspondent in previous practices, being ad hoc. There are many factors that can trigger a crisis, so their range needs to be expanded and preventive measures rethought so that legislation, prudential supervision, the intensity of international trade, financial innovations, customer expectations do not become a risk-taking spiral, but an issue. positive of the globalized economy;
- identifying the economic and social costs of a crisis. This step is also different in each country, depending on the scale of the crisis and its ability to manage it effectively. In this regard, it is necessary to identify the categories of participants affected and quantify the losses at the level of each institution, as well as its capacity to provide losses. Prevention involves much lower costs than remediation, so the first category of measures is the most important in the process of monitoring and maintaining financial stability. A special contribution to this process is the prudential supervision framework strengthened by the provisions of the Basel III agreement, as well as the efforts of the monetary authority to become a transparent, independent and credible structure.

Along with institutions and markets, another important pillar of ensuring financial stability is the identification of quantitative ways to assess financial stability.

Regarding the identification of the elements that ensure the stability of the financial system, Donath and Cismas have a distinct approach. The authors are not talking about measures that need to be taken but about certain conditions that need to be met in order to have a stable financial system (Donath & Cismas, 2008):

- favorable macroeconomic conditions obtained through policies aimed at sustainable economic growth, price stability, sound public finances or an adequate saving rate;
- appropriate structural conditions underpinned by taxation to promote initiative and competitive and efficient financial markets;
- an institutional infrastructure of financial markets that allows for the clear highlighting of the rights and obligations of participants in financial transactions.

Conclusions

Globalization aims at integrating national economies on various levels, economic, social, cultural, political, a phenomenon that can diminish the autonomy of governments, but the reconfiguration of social relations aims to increase the development potential of a country and, implicitly, the living standards of the population. The phenomenon of financial globalization favors, due to the increasing interdependencies between the world's economies, the risk of contagion, which triggers the spread of shocks at a rate that annihilates temporal and spatial barriers. All components of the financial system need an appropriate regulatory framework to maintain their stability, to contribute to the strengthening of the system, through viable strategies to achieve the objectives. Financial stability is a public good, subject to the principles of non-rivalry and non-exclusivity, but it must be the responsibility of every participant in the financial system, as undeserved benefit from positive externalities can have the impact of negative externalities. These are the advantages and disadvantages of the free market, connected to the springs of all the links of the system, globalized.

Financial stability must be seen as a continuum, not as an isolated moment in time and space. The financial system is also in a continuous stream of inputs and outputs in various forms, but it must maintain its ability to perform its functions at an acceptable level of performance, quantified by certain micro and macroeconomic variables.

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